

Energy Analysis of Cryptographic Algorithms in Server Environment

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Abstract

Cryptographic algorithms have varying resource requirements depending on their complexity, intended application, and the specific characteristics of the targeted computing environment. As they are computationally heavy, understanding the impact of energy consumption is vital for energy efficiency in computing. In this paper, we investigate energy consumption across various cryptographic algorithms, focusing in particular on LED, Piccolo, PRESENT, GIFT, and AES, and we assess their energy efficiency in a server environment.

The objective is to gain insights into the energy consumption patterns of selected algorithms, also aiming to identify the optimal trade-off between energy consumption and performance. By utilizing a monitoring tool to measure the energy consumed by the algorithms during their execution, we monitor data for each algorithm under different configurations. We systematically collect the energy data across various key sizes and implementation types and varying compiler optimization levels.

Our experiments yield detailed insights into the energy consumption of lightweight ciphers, we observe how energy usage varies with different key sizes and the impact of implementation choices, such as table-based, vperm, and bitslice methods. We also show how compiler optimization levels play a crucial role, offering opportunities for tailored configurations that balance energy efficiency and performance across varying cryptographic scenarios. The collected energy and performance data are a first and crucial step toward a more energy efficient deployment of cryptographic primitives in server environments and datacenters.

CCS Concepts

- **Hardware** → **Power estimation and optimization.**

Keywords

Block Ciphers, Energy Consumption, Intel RAPL

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1 Introduction

In the cryptography community, there is a growing interest in understanding the resource implications of cryptographic algorithms, especially in resource-constrained devices. Lightweight ciphers are specifically designed to suite devices that have restricted computing power or limited memory. Example of these devices are implantable devices, IoT, or certain type of embedded systems. The deployment of cryptographic primitives covers a diverse application domain. Research in cryptographic spans various dimensions, including security, efficiency, and adaptability to different computing environments. Understanding the energy footprint of cryptographic algorithms can help in optimizing resources, enabling informed algorithm selection, ultimately balancing security with efficiency.

In this paper, we focus on the energy consumption patterns of cryptographic algorithms when executed in servers environments and on the effects on these patterns caused by compiler optimizations. We compare the energy consumed by different configurations (multiple combinations of key sizes and implementation types) and we compare it with different implementations of the widely adopted encryption standard AES, used as reference.

We start our investigation by identifying the methods, the tools, and the applications that are needed to carry out the experiments. This task includes the definition of appropriated benchmarks. To evaluate the effects of different implementations styles and optimizations on the energy consumed, we create a benchmarks including several implementations of the same cryptographic algorithm realized with different design strategies. Each of the algorithm was then executed on a remote server, and we gathered energy performance through monitoring tools that leverage the sensors embedded into the processor of the target server. Data have been collected and analyzed using dedicated software routine. Using this tool chain, we achieve the main following contributions:

- We provide energy consumption patterns across varying key sizes (64/80/128/192/256 depending on the algorithm), and implementation styles (table based/vperm/bitsliced) for LED, Piccolo, and PRESENT. As reference, we include in our analysis three implementations of the AES algorithm.

- We report the effects of compiler optimization levels (such as levels 1,2,3, loop unrolling etc.) on the energy consumption of variants of the GIFT cipher compiled using the g++ compiler.
- We analyze our results and we discuss possible trade-off between energy efficiency and performance for the considered cryptographic algorithms.

While various parameters contribute to judging algorithm performance such as speed, throughput, etc., our particular emphasis on energy consumption stems from the importance of efficiency in current computing environments. Through the comparative analysis, our work contributes to a deeper understanding of the relationships between energy consumption, algorithm design, and compiler optimizations, also on larger computing machine, such as server processor. Such an in depth analysis, to date, was mostly carried out on the domain of resource constrained devices.

The remaining sections of the paper are structured as follows: In Section 2, we introduce the basics of cryptographic algorithms and block ciphers relevant for this paper, explaining the types, the implications of different key sizes and implementations methods that we consider in this paper. Section 3 overviews related studies previously presented in literature. Section 4 describes the design of the experiments, that are presented in details in Section 5. The obtained results are presented in Section 6, and discussed in Section 7. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 Background

2.1 Block Ciphers

Block ciphers are mathematical procedures that transform input data, the plaintext, it into an unreadable format, known as ciphertext. This process is called encryption. Block ciphers process data of fixed-size blocks, typically chunks of a fixed number of bits [14]. The process of encryption takes a secret, the secret key, and converts the plaintext of the given *blocksize* into a ciphertext of the same size. The security of the cipher is due to the fact that it is computationally difficult for an adversary to find the secret key given access to multiple plaintext/ciphertext pairs. The inverse procedure, called decryption, uses the same key used for the encryption process.

Key scheduling transforms the secret key into a series of round keys, essential for the encryption algorithms that are computed in several rounds. The core of a block cipher is the round function, that consists of various cryptographic operations like a non linear transformation (often called s-boxes), a permutation, and a mix operation [14]. Not all block ciphers include the exact set of components as the algorithm design can vary depending on the security level and the specific goals. Nevertheless, the following components represent common elements found in many modern block ciphers:

- **Input Block:** The data to be encrypted or decrypted is divided into fixed-size blocks. The block size is a critical parameter, often 64 or 128 bits.
- **Key Expansion:** The secret key provided by the user is expanded into a set of round keys. The key expansion algorithm generates a unique key for each encryption round.

- **Round Function:** The round function is the core operation performed in each encryption or decryption round. It typically includes a combination of substitution, permutation, and mixing operations to introduce confusion and diffusion. Many modern block ciphers, such as AES, use the SPN structure. It involves multiple rounds of substitution (S-box), permutation (P-box), and mixing operations.

2.2 Considered Ciphers

Here, we briefly explain the block ciphers that we considered in our study.

2.2.1 AES. AES [4] is a widely adopted symmetric block cipher, selected by the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) as the standard for encrypting sensitive information. It operates on fixed-size blocks and supports key lengths of 128, 192, or 256 bits. The block size of the AES algorithm is 128 bits, and it has an S-box of 8 bits. Despite it can be implemented even using an extremely limited amount of resources, AES can be often unsuitable for devices constrained by hardware limitations [10].

2.2.2 LED. The LED [17] block cipher suites constrained devices. It supports 64 and 128-bit key sizes, with an extremely small silicon footprint when compared with similar ciphers. LED main characteristics are the following. It introduces an ultra-light (virtually non-existent) key schedule and is robust against related-key attacks, supported by AES-like security proofs. Nevertheless, despite its hardware efficiency, LED performance in software are quite limited.

2.2.3 PRESENT. PRESENT [13] is a lightweight block cipher designed for devices with limited computational resources. It has a small key size and compact S-box design. It operates as an SP-network (Substitution-permutation layer) with 31 rounds, supporting a block length of 64 bits and key lengths of 80 and 128 bits. Furthermore PRESENT is specified as one of two lightweight encryption standards by ISO/IEC 29192-2:2012, and is hence one of the most important block ciphers.

2.2.4 Piccolo. Piccolo [21] is a 64-bit block cipher that supports both 80 and 128-bit keys, emphasizing efficiency and security for low-resource devices. Piccolo achieves a high level of security while maintaining a compact hardware occupation. Because of its compactness, Piccolo is suitable for extremely constrained devices such as RFID tags and sensor nodes. Furthermore, the block cipher was shown to consume very low energy per bit encrypted on custom ASIC hardware.

2.2.5 GIFT. GIFT [11] has a 128-bit key size and it is one of the most energy-efficient ciphers available today. It is primarily composed of S-boxes and permutations. Because of this, it can achieve good performance both, when implemented as area-optimized hardware or when implemented as software on high-end platforms. The block cipher was used as the underlying encryption primitive in 5 of the submissions to the recently concluded NIST competition on Lightweight cryptography and is regarded as one of the most important ciphers in the research community.

2.3 Implementation Methods

Cryptographic algorithms can be implemented in software in different ways. A software routine implementing a cryptography algorithm might be developed using an high-level programming language or an extremely low level one (such as assembly). Also, it can exploit a table based approach, where tables or arrays are pre-computed to enhance processing speed, or can have the functions being computed on the fly. More advanced techniques can be used, such as bitslicing, that involves parallelizing bitwise operations. Among all the choices, the implementation strategies we consider in this paper are:

- **Basic:** A basic cryptographic implementation is a direct translation of the algorithm’s mathematical description into code. It serves as a baseline implementation for demonstrating the workings principles of the algorithm but it is typically not optimized for performance or efficiency. This type of implementation is often used for reference purposes, providing a clear and comprehensible representation of the cryptographic processes involved.
- **Lightweight:** Lightweight implementations are designed to minimize the use of resources needed to compute the cryptographic algorithm they often trade limited use of resource with performance.
- **Vperm:** A Vperm (Vector Permutation) implementation leverages vector operations, capitalizing on modern processors’ Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD) capabilities. By processing multiple data simultaneously, Vperm implementations significantly enhance the speed and efficiency of cryptographic operations. This type of implementation is especially relevant for optimizing algorithms on platforms with advanced parallel processing capabilities.
- **Table-Based:** Table-based implementations of cryptographic algorithms utilize pre-computed tables to store intermediate values. These tables help speed-up computations, leading to improved performance. Commonly employed in symmetric ciphers, this approach enhances the performance of cryptographic operations by reducing the need for on-the-fly calculations.
- **Bitsliced:** Bitsliced implementations operate on multiple bits of data simultaneously, using bitwise operations to achieve high parallelism. This approach is particularly effective in symmetric-key cryptographic algorithms and are also known to be more robust against certain type of side channel attacks.

3 Related Work

Energy analysis, not only of cryptographic algorithm, has been subject of research since several years. In this section we summarize the most relevant work on energy analysis of cryptographic algorithms. Since no previous literature analyzed the problem on the server side, we concentrate in previous works that are anyway targeting platform that are larger than a typical IoT/small embedded devices. We start reporting works that assess the energy consumption of mobile computing devices and relatively large embedded devices.

In Potlapally *et al.* [20] energy consumption of battery-powered systems is evaluated by measuring the power consumed during

secure data transfer carried out using the SSL protocol, concentrating on the time-frame of cryptographic operations. This analysis provides insights into energy consumption patterns of asymmetric algorithms, hash algorithms, and the impact of key size on both asymmetric and symmetric algorithms. The study suggests that by adjusting key size and the number of rounds, cryptographic algorithms can be designed to operate more energy efficiently. While this study offers foundational knowledge, it is important to acknowledge that was published more than 15 years before our study (it was published in 2006) and, necessary, can not include the most recent research advancements in the field. Also, the work of Potlapally *et al.* includes energy analysis of different symmetric and asymmetric algorithms with only one implementation style for each algorithm. Our work, instead, includes symmetric block ciphers widely used today that were not existing at the time of the publication of the work of Potlapally *et al.* Furthermore, we explore different implementation strategies for each of the considered algorithm.

Wu *et al.* [23] evaluated three widely used encryption algorithms AES, Blowfish, and GOST by comparing their performance across different data block sizes. Key expansion time and encryption/decryption speed are measured, and simulation results are presented to showcase the effectiveness of each algorithm. Several conclusions are drawn from the analysis: Blowfish exhibits superior performance regardless of plaintext size, key expansion is a potential bottleneck for Blowfish, and decryption is the most time-consuming operation for AES. Although the research yields interesting results, its scope is limited by the number of algorithms evaluated. Also, it specifically examines the performance of algorithms executed on a smartphone, providing a perspective tailored to the mobile computing environment. In our work, we concentrate on the analysis on server environments.

Datsios *et al.* [16] explored the performance of three cryptographic algorithms: DES, AES, and RSA. Through thorough testing, the researchers measured power and energy consumption across different setups. The results yield valuable insights into the power and energy trade-offs associated with diverse architectural styles. Their analysis focuses around three key parameters crucial to power consumption in modern embedded processors. These parameters include the parallelism of the core, specifically the width and size of the execution window, the voltage and the frequency of the core. Additionally, they examine the impact of the size of the last-level cache (LLC). Notably, the findings highlight that, with specific parameters, cryptographic operations can be efficiently performed, achieving a good trade off between performance and power consumption. In our experiment, we do not enter into the underlying hardware architecture. Instead, we establish a baseline for the energy consumed by server processors executing cryptography at the granularity achievable by the monitoring tool used.

4 Design of Experiment

In this section we present the design of the experiments we carried out to assess the energy consumption of cryptographic algorithms on servers. This section details the environment and conditions

under which our experiments were conducted. It includes information about the hardware and software used, and any specific configurations, settings, or parameters.

4.1 Experimental Setup

To carry out our study, the target platform needs to fulfill few requirements. In addition to the obvious one of having sufficient computational power to execute the algorithms, the processor in the target platform should also have power sensors for measuring power consumption, and a monitoring tool capable of accessing and storing data from these sensors. Optionally, the platform could include a visualization tool to make monitoring and analysis more user friendly. Figure 1 offers a comprehensive overview of our setup, illustrating the interconnected components involved in the measurement process. The following subsection elaborates on each component and tool used in our experiments in details.

4.1.1 Server. The target server for our study runs Ubuntu on an Intel Xeon i7 CPU E5-2660 v2 @ 2.20GHz with a total of 20 physical cores. The target platform includes two sockets - *socket0* and *socket1* where each has 10 physical cores.

4.1.2 Power Measurement & and Monitoring tools. In this study, we leveraged the intrinsic capabilities of Intel processors, particularly the provision for monitoring performance events within the processors themselves. We use the Intel PCM [3]¹ tool that uses the built-in processor sensors to get the CPU's energy utilization. The PCM tool utilizes real-time data sourced from the performance monitoring units (PMU) integrated into Intel processors. Notably, the Xeon E5-2660 v2 is built upon the Sandy Bridge EP architecture. From the Sandy Bridge architecture, the Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) seamlessly integrated into the Power Monitoring Unit, has been introduced.

The RAPL [22] interface stores power consumption limits across different domains on a processor within a specified time frame. The power measurement logic in RAPL uses activity counters and predefined weights to capture accumulated energy, storing this information in 32-bit Machine State Registers (MSRs) [15] [18]. The Package (PKG) domain of RAPL measures the energy consumption of the entire processor socket, encompassing cores, integrated graphics, and uncore components such as last-level caches and the memory controller as depicted in Figure 2. The energy readings for the Package domain (PKG) are stored in the MSR_PKG_ENERGY_STATUS register. RAPL updates the counters every 1ms. Energy is quantified in units of Joules for PP0/PP1 (powerplane 0 and 1, Figure 2) RAPL Domains, as specified in the Intel processor architecture manual [2] for the Xeon E5-2600 processor family in section 15.10.1. While RAPL has the drawback of temporal resolution being limited to 1 millisecond, making it incapable of resolving events shorter than 1ms [15], this granularity is however acceptable for our experiments. Despite RAPL does not measure the actual power supplied, but instead uses performance counters to estimate it, it has a reasonable accuracy level [19]. Khan *et al.* [19] underlines the high correlation between RAPL readings and plug power, showing the achieved accuracy with minimal performance overhead. Since no

external power meter needs to be connected, using RAPL is a convenient and reliable way to carry out the measures we need in our experiments.

4.1.3 Visualization & Data Storage tool - Grafana & InfluxDB. The Intel PCM tool suite includes a command-line utilities that can be connected to graphical interfaces, such as the Grafana dashboard for visualization and to InfluxDB for storing the collected data. Grafana [1]² is an open-source platform designed for monitoring and observability, providing powerful visualization. Grafana has to be connected with a data source, that in our case is InfluxDB, to visualize, via a dedicated dashboard, the desired reporting, such as graphs and tables. Grafana fetches this data in real-time at specified intervals, in our case, every 2 seconds. The PCM collector exposes the energy data over HTTP in JSON format. Data are then collected using a dedicated APIs via Telegraf that is a server-based agent designed to collect and transmit metrics and events originated and stored into the InfluxDB database. Both the database and Grafana are executed as Docker containers on the host machine, while the access to the PCM utilities on the target machine is carried out via an SSH connection. This setup allows to collect the needed data, but also to dynamically query the database updating in real-time the graphs and tables on the dashboard.

4.2 Test Suite Design

To assess the energy consumption of cryptographic primitives and to evaluate the effects of implementations strategies and compile optimization on the energy consumption, we started from cryptographic codes available to the community and, from that, we constructed a comprehensive collection of cryptographic algorithms. We included algorithms that were fulfilling the following requirements:

- **Uniform Language Implementation:** All cryptographic algorithms included in the test suite should be implemented using the same programming language, ensuring consistency and facilitating comparative analysis.
- **Multiple Implementation Styles:** Each cryptographic algorithm should have been implemented using at least two different styles, allowing an evaluation of different approaches.
- **Different Key Sizes:** where supported, algorithms should be implemented with all the supported key size, allowing to assess the effects of key sizes on energy.
- **Minimal Dependency on Additional Software:** the source code of the selected algorithms should be standalone, and no additional libraries or external functions should be required to compute the algorithm itself.

For this paper, we selected C as implementation language, namely that the source code of all the selected algorithms has to be written in C. We allowed however an exception for GIFT, that is implemented in C++. This because GIFT is used to assess the effects of compilers optimization, thus it is not subjected to direct comparison with algorithms implemented in C.

¹Intel PCM Repository - <https://github.com/intel/pcm>

²Intel PCM Grafana Integration - <https://github.com/intel/pcm/tree/master/scripts/grafana>

Figure 1: Experimental setup

Figure 2: Power domains supported by RAPL [19]

For LED, Piccolo, and PRESENT, we used the source code included in the Cryptolib [8], an implementation provided by Benadjila *et al.* [12]. LED, PRESENT, and Piccolo adopt a 64-bit architecture characterized by the iteration of a round function, incorporating a 4-bit Sbox and a linear diffusion layer. The key schedule

in these ciphers is intentionally straightforward. The rationale behind selecting Cryptolib lies in the presence of several versions of the algorithms implemented using different implementation strategies, including table-based, vperm, and bit-sliced, each of them tailored to different key lengths and parallelism levels. For the AES algorithm, we used three different implementations. The first is a straightforward implementation of the algorithm [5], and serves as baseline for the AES energy consumption. The second is a light-weight implementation of the AES algorithm [9], and the third is a bit-sliced implementation [6]. To assess the influence of compiler optimizations, we included in the test bench the 128 bit-variant of the GIFT block cipher whose source code was obtained from [7]. Table 1 provides an overview of all the algorithms included in our experiments.

Algorithm	Implementation types	Key sizes	Repo.	Paper
LED	table, v-perm, bitsliced	64, 128	[8]	SAC 2013 [12]
PRESENT	table, v-perm, bitsliced	80, 128	[8]	SAC 2013 [12]
Piccolo	table, v-perm, bitsliced	80, 128	[8]	SAC 2013 [12]
AES - basic	Non-optimized	128, 192, 256	[5]	
AES - tiny	light-weight	128, 192, 256	[9]	
AES - bitsliced	bitsliced	128	[6]	
GIFT	light-weight	64-128, 128-128	[7]	CHES 2017 [11]

Table 1: Overview of the Tested Algorithms

4.3 Compiler selection and Configurations

The compilers we used in our experiments are the GCC and G++ compilers, that are part of the widely used open-source compiler suite GCC (GNU Compiler Collection). These compilers offer various levels of optimization. The ones we used in our experiments are described below, while the exact optimization flag used is reported in Table 7.

- **No Optimization:** Compiles code without applying any optimization techniques, prioritizing faster compilation over execution speed or code size.
- **Level 1 Optimization:** Basic optimizations focused on minimizing code size and improving execution speed at the cost of more extensive compile time.
- **Level 2 Optimization:** Enhanced optimizations beyond Level 1, aiming to strike a balance between code size and execution speed.
- **Level 3 Optimization:** Aggressive optimizations, prioritizing maximum execution speed over code size while requiring longer compilation times.
- **Native:** Compiler generates code specifically tailored for the specifies architecture, leveraging all available features and instructions.
- **Function Inlining:** Incorporates the body of a called function directly into its caller, potentially improving performance by reducing function call overhead.
- **Loop Vectorization:** Transforms loops to use SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) instructions, enhancing parallel execution and performance.
- **Loop Unrolling:** Expands loop iterations, potentially improving performance by reducing loop control overhead and allowing better compiler optimization opportunities.

ID	Type	Command with corresponding flags
#0	Basic	<code>g++ <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#1	Level-1 optimization	<code>g++ -O1 <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#2	Level-2 optimization	<code>g++ -O2 <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#3	Level-3 optimization	<code>g++ -O3 <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#4	Native	<code>g++ -march=native <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#5	Function Inlining	<code>g++ -finline-functions <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#6	Loop Vectorization	<code>g++ -ftree-vectorize <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>
#7	Loop Unrolling	<code>g++ -funroll-loops <fileToCompile.cpp> -o <outputExecutable></code>

Table 2: Compiler Optimization Flags

5 Implementation

First, we upload the cryptographic algorithms under test via an SFTP connection, then we initiate the energy monitoring process to collect relevant data. Each benchmark was executed 50'000 times.

The original source code for LED, PRESENT, and Piccolo have been modified adding the instrumentation needed to carry out the experiments. In particular, we added the following:

- To link the energy consumption with the function executed, custom code has been added to the main execution file to log timestamps of each execution.
- A custom bash script is added to repeat the execution for the intended number of iterations. All the execution parameters are passed using this script.
- Instrumentation to collect performance numbers, such as the collection of the cycles/byte needed for encryption and key scheduling, into a dedicated file has also been included via the header file.

As mentioned, for AES, we use three variants, the reference, a lightweight version called *Tiny-AES*, and a bitsliced one. For the first two variants, we modified the original main files to have separate main for each key size. This was done to not include in our energy measurements unnecessary branches due to the selection of the key size. Since for the bitsliced version supported only 128-bit key, we just added the scripts necessary to iterate the execution the needed amount of times.

The primary goal of the experiments on the GIFT block cipher is to evaluate the impact of compiler optimizations. We firstly determined the number of iterations for which the energy measurements were stable. Experiments for GIFT have been carried out by repeating each executing 10'000 times, since we empirically determined that this amount of execution was sufficient to ensure stability in the energy measurements. A binary file was generated for each compiler optimization and key length. The compilation commands, that correspond to all the compiler optimization evaluated for the GIFT algorithm, are outlined in Table 2.

We start the experiments by connecting to the target machine via an SSH connection and launching Intel PCM. Then, on the host machine, we started the Docker containers to run the software to collect and visualize the energy measures. Finally, a dedicated SSH connection is established from the host machine to the target one, to access the data collected by the Intel PCM tool. Once the measurement and visualization setup is up and running, the binary files of the cryptographic algorithms under test are sequentially executed, and the energy consumption data are collected either in CSV or in JSON format.

6 Results

In this section we report the energy consumption and performance figures we collected using the experimental setup and test benches presented in the previous sections.

6.1 Energy Consumption

Tables 3 to 7 report the energy consumption of LED, PRESENT, Piccolo, AES, and GIFT including all the variants considered in terms of key sizes and implementation strategies, each for 50000 iterations of a single encryption function.

In the tables, the blue-highlighted values denote the minimum energy consumption, while the red-highlighted values indicate the maximum within a specific configuration. The numerical entries in each cell report the energy consumption measured in joules, in the following form *average / maximum*. For each algorithm, we analyze the impact of the key size and the impact of the implementation strategy on the energy consumed.

6.1.1 LED. The results for the LED block cipher are reported in Table 3. We make the following observations:

- **Key Size:** For the table implementation, the energy consumption increases from 20.2 joules (key size 64) to 22.8 joules (key size 128). For the vperm implementation, the energy consumption increases from 23.6 joules (key size 64) to 23.9 joules (key size 128). For the bitsliced implementation, the energy consumption increases from 22.1 joules (key size 64) to 23.1

joules (key size 128). This suggests that, for all implementations, a larger key size results in higher energy consumption.

- **Implementation Strategy:**

For key size 64, the table implementation has the lowest energy consumption (20.2 joules), followed by bitsliced (22.1 joules) and vperm (23.6 joules). For key size 128, the bitsliced implementation has the lowest energy consumption (23.1 joules), followed by table (22.8 joules) and vperm (23.9 joules).

For LED cipher, the table-based implementations appears to be the most energy-efficient for both key sizes. The vperm implementation tends to have higher energy consumption compared to the other methods.

LED (joules)					
Key size = 64			Key size = 128		
table	vperm	bitsliced	table	vperm	bitsliced
20.2/23.7	23.6/24.3	22.1/24.2	22.8/24.3	23.9/24.4	23.1/24.2

Table 3: Energy consumption of the LED cipher varying key-sizes and implementation strategies

6.1.2 *PRESENT*. The results for the PRESENT algorithm are reported in Table 4.

- **Key Size:**

For the table implementation, the energy consumption decreases from 23.2 joules (key size 80) to 20.1 joules (key size 128). This suggests that, for the table implementation, a larger key size results in lower energy consumption. For the vperm implementation, the energy consumption increases from 22.2 joules (key size 80) to 23.7 joules (key size 128). This indicates that, for the vperm implementation, a larger key size leads to higher energy consumption. For the bitsliced implementation, the energy consumption increases slightly from 21.0 joules (key size 80) to 23.2 joules (key size 128). This suggests that, for the bitsliced implementation, there is a modest increase in energy consumption with a larger key size.

- **Implementation Strategy:**

For key size 80, the bitsliced implementation has the lowest energy consumption (21.0 joules), followed by vperm (22.2 joules) and table (23.2 joules). For key size 128, the table implementation has the lowest energy consumption (20.1 joules), followed by bitsliced (23.2 joules) and vperm (23.7 joules).

When comparing implementation strategies, bitsliced exhibits lower energy consumption for key size 80, while the table based implementation is more energy-efficient for key size 128. The vperm implementation tends to have higher energy consumption compared to the other methods.

6.1.3 *Piccolo*. The results for the Piccolo algorithm are reported in Table 5.

PRESENT (joules)					
Key size = 80			Key size = 128		
table	vperm	bitsliced	table	vperm	bitsliced
23.2/24.8	22.2/24.7	21/24.6	20.1/23.3	23.7/24.4	23.2/24

Table 4: Energy consumption of the PRESENT cipher varying Key-sizes and implementation strategies

- **Key Size:**

For the table implementation, the energy consumption increases from 20.7 joules (key size 80) to 23.8 joules (key size 128). For the vperm implementation, the energy consumption decreases from 24.0 joules (key size 80) to 21.6 joules (key size 128). For the bitsliced implementation, the energy consumption increases from 21.4 joules (key size 80) to 22.9 joules (key size 128). Hence, a larger key size results in higher energy consumption except for vperm.

- **Implementation Strategy:**

For key size 80, the table implementation has the lowest energy consumption (20.7 joules), followed by bitsliced (21.4 joules) and vperm (24.0 joules). For key size 128, the vperm implementation has the lowest energy consumption (21.6 joules), followed by bitsliced (22.9 joules) and table (23.8 joules)

For Piccolo, the table-based implementations are the most energy-efficient for 80-bit key sizes. The vperm implementation tends to have good energy consumption compared to the other implementations for key size 128. Bitsliced stays in between for both key sizes.

Piccolo (joules)					
Key size = 80			Key size = 128		
table	vperm	bitsliced	table	vperm	bitsliced
20.7/24.2	24/25.4	21.4/24.3	23.8/24.6	21.6/24.5	22.9/24.4

Table 5: Energy consumption of the Piccolo cipher varying Key-sizes and implementation strategies

6.1.4 *AES*. The results for the AES algorithm are reported in Table 6

- **Key Size Impact:**

Among the basic implementation type, the energy consumption increases with the key size, peaking at AES-basic-192. Among the tiny implementation type, there is a slight increase in energy consumption with the key size, with AES-tiny-256 having the highest value.

- **Implementation Strategy:**

For the key size of 128, the tiny implementation type consumes the least energy (18.1 joules), followed by bitslice (21.3 joules), and basic (27 joules). For the key size of 192, tiny again consumes the least (18.3 joules), followed by basic which consumes the most (29.8 joules). For the key size of

256, tiny consumes the least (19.3 joules), followed by basic which again consumes the most (27.7 joules).

The measures suggest that the AES-tiny generally exhibits lower energy consumption compared to the basic and bitsliced ones. The basic implementation type shows the highest energy consumption for key size 192, while the tiny implementation has the highest energy consumption for the version using a 256 key.

AES (joules)						
basic			tiny			bitsliced
128	192	256	128	192	256	128
27/41	29.8/39	27.7/40.7	18.1	18.3	19.3	21.3/23.1

Table 6: Energy Consumption for the AES cipher varying Key-sizes and implementation strategy

6.1.5 GIFT. Using the GIFT algorithm, we explored the effects of different compiler optimization. The energy consumed by GIFT64 and GIFT128 algorithms are reported in Table 7. From these, the following observations could be made:

ID	Type	GIFT64 (joules)		GIFT128 (joules)	
		Avg	Max	Avg	Max
#0	Basic	17.6	22.5	21.2	31.5
#1	Level-1 optimization	16.7	23.4	16.4	37.8
#2	Level-2 optimization	14.6	22.7	22.3	29.7
#3	Level-3 optimization	16.2	21.8	23.6	29.6
#4	Native	17.6	25.5	26	34.2
#5	Function Inlining	16.5	22	28.5	39.7
#6	Loop Vectorization	16.9	29.8	18.2	30.8
#7	Loop Unrolling	16.4	25.6	26.9	39.1

Table 7: Energy consumption for the GIFT cipher using different compiler configurations

- Compiler optimizations significantly influence energy consumption. Notably, level-2 optimization tends to result in the lowest energy consumption for GIFT64, while function inlining and loop vectorization show mixed impacts across configurations.
- Generally, GIFT128 exhibits higher energy consumption than GIFT64 across various compiler configurations and optimization levels. This is expected as larger block sizes often require more computational resources.
- Level-2 optimization consistently achieves low energy consumption for GIFT64, but its impact varies for GIFT128, where level-1 optimization sometimes performs better. This suggests that the optimization that achieves the highest energy efficiency is not always the same, but it varies depending on the block size and specific characteristics of the algorithm.

- The Native configuration tends to increase energy consumption, particularly for GIFT128. This could be attributed to architecture-specific optimizations that may not align with the algorithm’s characteristics.
- Function inlining and loop vectorization show varying impacts on energy consumption. While function inlining tends to reduce energy consumption for GIFT64, it increases it for GIFT128. Loop vectorization also has mixed effects on energy consumption.
- Loop unrolling tends to have a positive impact on energy consumption, particularly for GIFT128 where it reduces both average and maximum values.

6.2 Performance Results

As often done in the domain, we reported the performance of the algorithms considered in this study as “cycles per byte”. This measure reports the number of clock cycles required to process one byte of data through the algorithm. Hence, a lower cycle per byte value indicates better performance. The performance of LED, PRESENT and Piccolo for all the considered variants, measured as average cycles/byte, are reported in Table 8, Table 9, and Table 10, respectively.

LED - perf (cycles/byte)					
Key size = 64			Key size = 128		
table	vperm	bitsliced	table	vperm	bitsliced
128.9	73.8	38.42	187.5	112.8	50.54

Table 8: Performance of the LED algorithm (cycles/byte)

PRESENT - perf (cycles/byte)					
Key size = 80			Key size = 128		
table	vperm	bitsliced	table	vperm	bitsliced
222.8	130.2	40.3	225.04	133.8	45.54

Table 9: Performance of the PRESENT algorithm (cycles/byte)

Piccolo - perf (cycles/byte)					
Key size = 80			Key size = 128		
table	vperm	bitsliced	table	vperm	bitsliced
156.2	71.94	34.3	201.1	89.1	36.5

Table 10: Performance of the Piccolo algorithm (cycles/byte)

As expected, a consistent pattern emerges in performance values upon examination of various implementations (table, vperm, bit-slice) for LED, PRESENT, and Piccolo across key sizes (64/80/128).

The bitslice implementation consistently exhibits the lowest cycles per byte, while the table-based implementation achieves the highest. The vperm implementation falls between the other two. As mentioned, such a pattern was expected. These results, in fact, align with the results presented by Benadjila *et al.* [12] for an XEON X5650 processor running at 2.67GHz. The consistently lower cycles per byte for bitslice implementations suggest more efficient processing of data compared to table-based implementations. This efficiency may be advantageous in scenarios where computational resources or processing speed are critical factors. Bitslicing processes data by representing each bit of a word independently, allowing for parallel bitwise operations. This inherent parallelism aligns well with modern processors that excel at parallel computation. Table-based implementations often exhibit lower efficiency compared to bitslice counterparts due to the inherent reliance on table lookups and more complex operations. In a table-based approach, the algorithm typically involves using precomputed tables to substitute complex operations like S-box substitutions or other non-linear transformations. These table lookups introduce memory access overhead and potential cache misses, especially when the tables are large or irregularly accessed. The observed pattern may also reflect a design trade-off in favor of efficiency (bitslice) or simplicity (table). Vperm implementations, consistently falling between bitslice and table values, may be seen as a compromise between efficiency and simplicity. Depending on the specific application requirements, vperm implementations might provide a reasonable trade-off between performance and ease of implementation.

7 Discussion

7.1 Table-based Vs Vperm Vs Bitslice

The analysis of the energy consumption reveals a clear distinction between lightweight and non-lightweight implementations of cryptographic algorithms. It is evident that lightweight implementations consistently consume significantly less energy than their basic, unoptimized counterparts. This can be seen clearly in Figure 3, Table 6 and Table 11 where it is possible to see in details that a non-optimized version of AES (AES128, AES192, and AES256 in blue bars) consumes a higher amount of energy. Among the lightweight ciphers, the lowest average energy usage, approximately 20 joules, is observed for table-based implementations of LED, Piccolo, and PRESENT. On the other hand, vperm implementations exhibit the highest average energy consumption among lightweight ciphers, reaching up to 24 joules.

Figure 3: Effects of implementation types on LED, PRESENT, Piccolo, and AES

For table-based implementations, as observed by Benadjila *et al.* [12], we need to consider the trade off between the size of the used tables and the number of operations computed by the algorithm. In particular, larger tables result in a reduction of operations during the round function, but they also bring an increased latency in table lookups. In essence, we need to trade the decrease in computational workload with higher lookup latency. PRESENT128 and LED64 show the best average energy levels for table-based (20.2 joules), Piccolo128 for vperm (21.6 joules), and PRESENT80 (21 joules) for bitslice.

Interestingly, lightweight implementation seems to be promising also on the server side. In fact, the AES-tiny 128-bit implementation stands out as the most energy-efficient option, achieving the lowest observed energy consumption, showing the efficiency gains achieved through lightweight design and optimization strategies. Although this is usually the case for embedded and tiny devices, it was not straightforward to expect that similar considerations would hold also in server environments.

Figure 4: AES energy consumption pattern

7.2 Smaller vs Bigger key-sizes or Block sizes

Typically, larger key sizes increase the complexity of the computation, potentially leading to increased energy consumption. This expectation is confirmed by our experiments. This distinction becomes particularly evident in the PRESENT algorithm, as reported in Figure 3 and Table 11, where the number of rounds remains the same for both key sizes (80 and 128). Despite the same number of rounds, the energy consumption for PRESENT128 is higher than that for PRESENT80 for both, vperm and bitslice methods. The energy consumption for the AES algorithm is reported in Figure 4. For AES the impact of keysize is less pronounced but it exists nevertheless. For instance, within the AES algorithm, the AES-tiny-128 implementation highlights the efficiency of smaller key sizes, consuming an average of 18.0 joules compared to AES-tiny-256’s 19.3 joules.

In the LED algorithm, the LED128-table implementation consumes more energy (22.8 joules) than the LED64-table (20.2 joules). This pattern is also present for different block sizes of the GIFT

Algorithm	No. of Rounds	Table(basic for AES) (joules)	Vperm(tiny for AES) (joules)	Bitslice (joules)
LED64	32	20.2	23.6	22.1
LED128	48	22.8	23.9	23.1
Present80	31	23.2	22.2	21
Present128	31	20.1	23.7	23.2
Piccolo80	25	20.7	24	21.4
Piccolo128	31	23.8	21.6	22.9
AES128	10	27	18.1	21.3
AES192	12	29.8	18.3	-
AES256	14	27.7	19.3	-

Table 11: Energy Consumption Data in joules

algorithm’s, as visible for instance in the “Function Inlining” configuration in Figure 5 and Table 7, where GIFT128 consistently consumes more energy than GIFT64 (average of 28.5 joules and 16.5 joules, respectively). These instances highlight the general trend that larger key sizes and block sizes tend to correlate with higher energy consumption.

7.3 Impact of Compiler Optimization

As showed in the case of the GIFT algorithm, reported in Figure 5, different compiler optimizations do affect the energy consumption. GIFT64 demonstrates lower energy consumption with level-2 optimization, suggesting that these compiler configurations might be more effective for specific algorithmic structures. Function inlining tends to increase energy usage, likely due to the expanded code size, while loop vectorization and loop unrolling do not show a consistent trend, with GIFT64 benefiting from loop unrolling but GIFT128 showing an increase in energy consumption.

Figure 5: Energy consumption for different compiler optimizations for the GIFT algorithm

A noteworthy observation, highlighted in Figure 5 by red circles, is that with level-2 optimization GIFT64 and GIFT128 achieved nearly identical energy consumption. Similarly, the energy consumption during loop vectorization closely aligns for GIFT64 and GIFT128.

Figure 6: LED, PRESENT, Piccolo performance summary

7.4 Tradeoff between Performance and Energy consumption

Figure 6 shows a summary of the performances of LED, PRESENT, and Piccolo. We notice that the general trend is that a decrease in the cycles/ per byte metric is usually accompanied by a decrease in the energy consumption.

Figure 7: LED - Energy vs Performance

Figure 7 shows the energy consumption and the performance of the different implementation of the LED algorithm. As expected, LED128 requires more clock cycles per byte to be computed, compared to LED64, and also with the cost of slightly higher energy

consumption as shown in figure 7. In contrast, PRESENT has relatively high energy consumption and comparatively moderate performance. Also, the performance difference between PRESENT80 and PRESENT128 for all three implementation styles is limited. For Piccolo, reported in Figure 9, the bitslice implementation offers optimal performance both with respect to performance and energy. Between Piccolo80 and Piccolo128, table-based and vperm show better performance for Piccolo80, while in bitslice the cycles per byte remain in close range for both key sizes.

Figure 8: PRESENT - Energy vs Performance

In conclusion, vperm implementations show much better performance than table-based, while bitslice has a clear pattern of being the best performing one among the three. Considering that the table-based method might also have increased energy consumption caused by the table lookups in memory (which are not measured with our setup), the bitslice method seems to be the one offering the best energy / performance figures. This could be because a significant portion of the encryption cost stems from the Sbox lookups, which the bitslice representation mitigates this by computing the Sbox as a sequence of Boolean operations within a few clock cycles as noted in [12].

8 Conclusion

In this paper we explored the energy consumption of cryptographic algorithms on server environments. In particular, we analyzed the effects that implementation styles, key sizes, and compiler optimization might have on energy consumption of these algorithms. Our measurements, obtained using the Intel PCM tool, indicates that lightweight implementations tend to exhibit lower energy consumption, with bitslice methods outperforming other implementation styles. However, the average energy consumption range remains relatively close among these lightweight ciphers for a large number of execution iterations. Key size impacts and implementation method comparisons shed light on energy efficiency variations that can be used for security considerations, optimizing computational complexity, and energy efficiency in cryptographic

Figure 9: Piccolo - Energy vs Performance

algorithms. Additionally, the analysis of compiler optimization on the GIFT algorithm showed that such optimizations have a non negligible effect on energy consumption.

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